

Some Competing Accelerated Life Testing Models

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Abstract

Several competing accelerated life testing models have been studied for modeling accelerated failure times by many authors (see Nelson, 1981). This article briefly reviews several aspects and properties of some competing accelerated life testing models namely the log-normal, the inverse Gaussian, and the gamma models that have a wide appeal. In these situations, modeling of the mean time to failure is modeled as a function of the stress variable, while assuming other parameter(s) to be constant. In this paper we considered the modeling of coefficient of variation also as a function of the stress variable. We propose a Bayesian approach for finding a point estimate as well as credible interval estimate for the coefficient of variation under the assumption that the data are drawn from one of the above three distributions.

Key words: Inverse Gaussian Model; Log-normal Model; Gamma Model; Coefficient of Variation; Bayesian Approach.

1 Introduction

‘Accelerated life test’ (ALT) applies to the type of study where failure times can be accelerated by applying higher ‘stress’ to the component, that is, where higher stress may bring quicker failure of the component. For example, some components may fail quicker at a higher temperatures, however, it may take a longer time before failure occurs at lower temperatures. The variable or a combination of variables, such as temperature and pressure, that may accelerate failure is generally called ‘stress’ factor. The need for an accelerated life test in practice arises where the objective is to study the relation between failure and stress conditions. At low ‘stress’ conditions, the time required may be sufficiently large for its reliability estimation which can be tested under higher stress factors terminating the experiment in a relatively shorter time. By this process the failures which in normal conditions would occur only after a long testing can be observed quicker and the size of data can be increased without a large cost and long time. In contrast, accelerated life testing provides economic collection of data in order to be able to estimate the reliability that can be projected at the lower stress level, through appropriate models. In ALTs, test units are subjected to the elevated stress levels, and then the test results are extrapolated from the test conditions to the normal operating condition using a reasonable statistical model. The common failure mechanism is considered as a necessary condition for the extrapolated procedure in ALT.

For the extrapolation of higher stress mechanism to the lower stress situation, the unit lifetime is assumed to follow a parametric distribution, assuming the mean time to failure (MTTF) to be a function of the stress variable, while assuming other parameter(s) to be constant. For example, assuming the Weibull distribution as the failure time model, engineers can conclude that the failure mechanisms are the same if the shape parameters of Weibull distributions at different stress levels are equal. In this paper, we propose (see Section 2) modeling of the Coefficient of Variation (CV) that is often used as a measure of heterogeneity or lack of uniformity in a population in practice where variable of interest is positive, as a function of the stress variable as well. Let the mean and

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standard deviation of the random variable X be denoted by ν and σ respectively. The coefficient of variation (CV) is defined as the ratio of σ/ν . In practice, CV is used in situations yielding positive measurements (Johnson and Welch, 1940), Gaussian distribution based approaches are presumably applied in such studies. An obvious estimate of CV based on a random sample of size n is given by the ratio of the sample standard deviation S and the sample mean \bar{X} , namely the sample CV $\hat{\theta} = S/\bar{X}$.

Several authors have discussed the estimation of common CV for normal populations. There are several real life situations in industry and agriculture, where the variable of interest is in positive range [Chhikara and Folks (1977, 1989), Takagi *et al.* (1997), Chaubey *et al.* (2017), Singh (1993), Chapter 15 of Johnson *et al.* (1994), among others] and follows inverse Gaussian (IG) distribution. In fact, the key parameters to verify whether the failure mechanisms are same under the parametric model are generally related to the coefficient of variation. For example, Meeker and Escobar (1998) analyzed the temperature-accelerated lifetime data of a particular kind device by using lognormal model, and assessed the reasonableness of the constant scale parameter. Yin *et al.* (2017) studied specimens of solid epoxy electrical insulation in an accelerated voltage life test using power-Weibull distribution based on the assumption of the fixed shape parameter. In lognormal and Weibull cases, the coefficients of variation only depends on the scale parameter and the shape parameter respectively. Thus it is reasonable to compare the coefficients of variation at different stress levels in order to show the consistency of the failure mechanisms.

2 Models for Failure Time Data

In stochastic modeling of failure time, the fatigue life time distribution leads to a prominent role in the engineering literature. Bhattacharyya and Fries (1982) assumed the fatigue to be governed by a Wiener process, and the time to failure distributed as the first passage time distribution, providing an inverse Gaussian model for the failure time. For a stochastic relation of the failure time (Y) to the intensity of stress x , (often assumed to be inversely proportional to the stress level), we have assumed here that the severity of the stress levels does not change the form of the life time distribution but the stress levels have an influence on the value of the parameters. In this case, parameter ν is taken most important role to have a direct relation to x because it measures the mean fatigue growth per unit time. Since, in accelerated life testing, it may be assumed that higher stress produces smaller mean failure time, they considered the following simple model

$$\nu(x) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x$$

In a practical situation, we only consider $\gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x > 0$ on a finite interval of x which corresponds to the range of stress x . But we assume that the origin is taken at the lower point of this interval, i.e. γ_0 . In this paper we explore only the simple linear form, though this may be generalized to polynomial forms, to describe nonlinear relations.

We would like to consider some general family of distributions in accelerated life testing. These distributions have the structure of an exponential family and its many properties are associated with sampling distributions. Its derivation from a stochastic formulation of the failure process provides a physical support to its exact fit. Nelson (1975) presented statistical methods for planing and analyzing accelerated life tests with the Arrhenius model. This model should be of interest for estimating life which as a function of temperature because test units are not limited to just accelerating variable but they are applicable to many accelerated life tests with other accelerating variables, where for a given temperature, the life distribution is log-normal. The logarithmic standard deviation of the distribution is constant. The mean function $\mu(x)$ of the logarithmic life is a linear function *i.e.*

$$\mu(x) = \alpha + \beta x.$$

To estimate the regression function, a lognormal model simplifies the analysis, however this may not be appropriate as we demonstrate in the following example that presents data from Gnedenko *et al.* (1999) on life times of new Class-H motor insulation (see the data below) Nelson (1971) reports data on the failure of 40 motorettes with a new class-H insulation material in a motorette

Table 1: Hours to failure for class-H insulation material

<u>190⁰C</u>	<u>220⁰C</u>	<u>240⁰C</u>	<u>260⁰C</u>
7228	1764	1175	600
7228	2436	1175	744
7228	2436	1521	744
8448	2436	1569	744
9167	2436	1617	912
9167	2436	1665	1128
9167	3108	1665	1320
9167	3108	1713	1464
10511	3108	1761	1608
10511	3108	1953	1896

Table 2: Mean and CV for different stress level

MTTF	8782.20	2637.6000	1581.4000	1116.0000
S. D.	1244.0117	453.5654	244.2745	439.2357
CV	14.165	17.196	15.447	39.3587

test performed at four elevated temperature setting run at 190⁰C, 220⁰C, 240⁰C and 260⁰C. For each test temperature, the 10 motorettes were periodically examined for insulation failure and then given failure time is midway between the inspection time when the failure was found and the time of the previous inspection.

The linear regression model required to estimate the mean time to failure at different stress levels assumes a constant error variance that necessarily implies a constant coefficient of variation. However, in the above data this may be violated, and therefore we may be tempted to use alternative regression relations and/or other lifetime distributions. A regression relation of $Y = \log(T)$ on $x = 10^5 / (8.6171 * Temp)$ where $Temp$ is measured on a Kelvin scale, i.e.

$$Temp = Temp \text{ in Celsius} + 180.15.$$

The regression equation is

$$y = -7.28 + 0.649x$$

Figure 1: Mean and CV for different stress levels

This output shows a good fit on the log-scale ($R^2 = 91\%$), however, in order to desire an improvement in modeling a quadratic relation may be better. This provides only a slight improvement; R^2 increase from 91% to 92%. On the other hand using a quadratic model regression the TTF on X produces $R^2 = 95\%$. With this example in the background we propose to investigate the modeling the mean (ν) and coefficient of variation (CV) θ of life times T ,

$$\nu(x) = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x; \theta(x) = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z; z = 1/x.$$

Note that we have listed simple regression relations only; in general we may consider polynomial relations for ν and θ . Next we describe the most common accelerated failure probability models of the distribution of T that we will consider for further discussion in the following subsections.

3 Some ALT Models with ν, θ Parametrization

3.1 Log-normal model

The lognormal density considers the mean and variance parameter for the distribution of $\log(T)$ that is given by

$$f(y|\mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{y\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\ln(y)-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

with $\mu = \log \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{1+\theta^2}}; \sigma^2 = \log(1 + \theta^2)$.

The re-parameterized form in terms of (ν, θ) follows due to the following results on the log-normal random variable.

$$\nu = E(T) = \exp\left(\mu + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right) \text{ and } \theta = \sqrt{\frac{V(T)}{\nu^2}},$$

$Var(T) = (e^{\sigma^2} - 1)e^{2\mu+\sigma^2} = \nu^2(e^{\sigma^2} - 1)$ Therefore, the one-to-one relation between (μ, σ) and (ν, θ) is given by

$$\mu = \log \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{1+\theta^2}}; \sigma^2 = \log(1 + \theta^2)$$

In the context of Bayesian inference, we consider direct modeling of MTTF as

$$T_{ij} \sim \text{lognormal}(\nu_j = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x_j; \theta_j = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z_j)$$

with the likelihood function given by

$$L(\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \delta_0, \delta_1 | \mathbf{T}) = \prod_{j=1}^k \prod_{i=1}^{n_j} f(T_{ij} | \nu_j = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x_j; \theta_j = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z_j)$$

where $\mathbf{T} = \{\mathbf{T}_1, \mathbf{T}_2, \dots, \mathbf{T}_k\}; T_j = \{T_{1j}, T_{2j}, \dots, T_{n_j j}\}$ and

$$f(y|\nu, \theta) = \frac{1}{y\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\ln(y)-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

with $\mu = \log \frac{\nu}{\sqrt{1+\theta^2}}; \sigma^2 = \log(1 + \theta^2)$.

Specification of priors for $\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \delta_0, \delta_1$:

For simplicity we propose vague priors for each component,

$$p(\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \delta_0, \delta_1) = p(\gamma_0)p(\gamma_1)p(\delta_0)p(\delta_1)$$

where

$$p(\gamma_0) = \frac{1}{b_0 - a_0} I_{[a_0, b_0]}(\gamma_0)$$

$$p(\gamma_1) = \frac{1}{b_1 - a_1} I_{[a_1, b_1]}(\gamma_1)$$

$$p(\delta_0) = \frac{1}{d_0 - c_0} I_{[c_0, d_0]}(\delta_0)$$

$$p(\delta_1) = \frac{1}{d_1 - c_1} I_{[c_1, d_1]}(\delta_1)$$

where $a_0, b_0, a_1, b_1, c_0, d_0, c_1, d_1$ are specified by expert opinion. More flexible modeling with normal priors (with mean and precision information) may be specified, however we have not considered it here. With these specifications we propose to use Gibbs sampler to find the posterior of the parameters and the corresponding credible intervals using HPD region.

3.2 Gamma model

For the gamma model with shape parameter α and scale parameter β , the density is given by

$$f(y|\alpha, \beta) = 1/\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha) t^{\alpha-1} e^{-x/\beta}$$

We may note that the (ν, θ) parametrization is obtained by the relations

$$\nu = \alpha\beta; \theta^2 = 1/\alpha$$

and the corresponding likelihood function and prior similar to those given in the lognormal case.

$$L(\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \delta_0, \delta_1 | \mathbf{T}) = \prod_{j=1}^k \prod_{i=1}^{n_j} f(T_{ij} | \nu_j = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x_j; \theta_j = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z_j)$$

where

$$f(y|\nu, \theta) = \frac{1}{\beta^\alpha \Gamma(\alpha)} y^{\alpha-1} e^{-y/\beta},$$

for $\alpha = 1/\theta^2; \beta = \nu\theta^2$.

3.3 Inverse Gaussian model

For the inverse Gaussian model the density with (ν, θ) parametrization is given by

$$f(t|\nu, \theta) = \left(\frac{\nu}{2\pi\theta^2 t^3} \right)^{1/2} \exp \left\{ -\frac{1}{2\theta^2} \frac{(t - \mu)^2}{\mu t} \right\}.$$

and the likelihood function is given by

$$L(\gamma_0, \gamma_1, \delta_0, \delta_1 | \mathbf{T}) = \prod_{j=1}^k \prod_{i=1}^{n_j} f(T_{ij} | \nu_j = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 x_j; \theta_j = \delta_0 + \delta_1 z_j)$$

and the Bayesian computation may follow naturally.

4 Conclusions

The intervals for uniform distribution as vague priors (Lower = estimate - K*SE, Upper = estimate + K*SE). Although the number of observations was small ($n = 10$), the studied distributions showed reasonably close fit at each stress level. The stability or relative variation measured as coefficient of variation (CV) was the main point of study with a view that it may be constant over the stress levels. For the Bayesian estimation, we used the vague priors for the regression coefficients in relationship of mean (ν) and CV(θ) with the stress level. The posterior mean ν showed decreasing trend with the stress level. Posterior mean of the coefficient of variation (θ)

Table 3: The intervals for uniform distribution as vague priors

Distribution	K	(a0, b0)	(a1, b1)	(c0, d0)	(c1, d1)
LN	.001	(-21280.88, -21167.12)	(476.91, 479.09)	(-0.4792, -0.4708)	(34.79, 35.21)
Gamma	.10	(-21792.8, -20655.2)	(467.1, 488.9)	(-0.517, -0.433)	(32.9, 37.1)
IG	.01	(-21280.88, -21167.12)	(476.91, 479.09)	(-0.4792, -0.4708)	(34.79, 35.21)

Table 4: Goodness of fit Statistics and Criterion

Temperature		LN	Gamma	IG
190°C	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic	0.2508	0.2428	0.2489
	Cramer-von Mises Statistic	0.1120	0.1065	0.1095
	Anderson-Darling Statistic	0.7358	0.6974	0.7061
	Akaike's Information Criterion	174.0	173.9	174.0
	Bayesian Information Criterion	174.6	174.5	174.6
220°C	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic	0.2629	0.2650	0.2550
	Cramer-von Mises Statistic	0.1763	0.1761	0.1695
	Anderson-Darling Statistic	1.0957	1.0622	1.0112
	Akaike's Information Criterion	154.6	154.2	154.6
	Bayesian Information Criterion	155.2	154.8	155.2
240°C	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic	0.2230	0.2149	0.2326
	Cramer-von Mises Statistic	0.1162	0.1052	0.1186
	Anderson-Darling Statistic	0.7995	0.7029	0.7336
	Akaike's Information Criterion	142.5	142.0	142.4
	Bayesian Information Criterion	143.1	142.6	143.0
260°C	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic	0.2268	0.2129	0.2163
	Cramer-von Mises Statistic	0.0716	0.0619	0.0637
	Anderson-Darling Statistic	0.4296	0.3758	0.3813
	Akaike's Information Criterion	151.6	151.8	151.4
	Bayesian Information Criterion	152.2	152.4	152.0

tended to increase with the stress level, for each distribution. The widths of credible intervals for CV: θ were found shortest of the IG distribution followed by the lognormal and widest for the Gamma distribution. The priors assumed are vague priors and the inference is dominated by likelihood. In reality, they should be replaced by subjective priors.

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Table 5: Fitted distribution parameters' estimates

Distribution	Parameter	190°C	220°C	240°C	260°C
LN	meanlog	9.072	7.864	7.355	6.952
	sdlog	0.133	0.162	0.145	0.361
Gamma	shape	55.380	37.57	46.57	7.17
	rate	0.006	0.01425	0.029	0.0064
IG	mean	8782	2638	1581	1116
	shape	467627	86888	63791	7631

Table 6: Posterior means and 95% CI for the CV at stress levels

Distribution	Stress	CV	Mean	SD	Median	Coverage	LCL	UCL	Width
LN	190°C	θ_1	0.0981	0.0003	0.0981	0.9502	0.0975	0.0987	0.0115
	220°C	θ_2	0.1885	0.0003	0.1885	0.9504	0.1879	0.1891	0.0123
	240°C	θ_3	0.2489	0.0003	0.2489	0.9504	0.2482	0.2495	0.0129
	260°C	θ_4	0.3092	0.0003	0.3092	0.9501	0.3085	0.3098	0.0134
Gamma	190°C	θ_1	0.0984	0.0002	0.0985	0.9504	0.0980	0.0988	0.0211
	220°C	θ_2	0.1890	0.0002	0.1890	0.9500	0.1885	0.1893	0.0225
	240°C	θ_3	0.2493	0.0002	0.2493	0.9500	0.2488	0.2497	0.0235
	260°C	θ_4	0.3096	0.0002	0.3097	0.9500	0.3091	0.3100	0.0246
IG	190°C	θ_1	0.0984	0.0002	0.0984	0.9501	0.0979	0.0988	0.0029
	220°C	θ_2	0.1889	0.0002	0.1889	0.9508	0.1884	0.1893	0.0031
	240°C	θ_3	0.2492	0.0002	0.2492	0.9505	0.2487	0.2496	0.0032
	260°C	θ_4	0.3095	0.0003	0.3096	0.9507	0.3090	0.3100	0.0034

Figure 2: Log-normal distribution for different stress level

Figure 3: Gamma distribution for different stress level

Figure 4: Inverse Gaussian distribution for different stress level

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